

A MODEL FOR UNDERSTANDING THE ENHANCEMENT OF THE YOUNG'S MODULUS OF MACROSCOPIC CARBON NANOTUBE FIBRES DUE TO POLYMER INFILTRATION

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ABSTRACT

We have produced macroscopic Carbon Nanotube Fibres (CNTF) through chemical vapour deposition (CVD) and infiltrated them with several polymers *via* solution infiltration. Here we study the mechanisms of stress transfer that take place within the CNTF when the composite specimens are subjected to axial tension. We have monitored this effect through *in-situ* Raman spectroscopy. This enabled us to determine the mechanical consequences of infiltrating the fibre with polymer and its relationship to the mass fraction of CNTF in each composite (w_f). Unlike traditional composite materials, which follow the rule of mixtures, we observe an important increase of the Young's modulus of up to 50% when the CNTF is infiltrated with polymer. The enhancement is observable for up to a critical fibre mass fraction of 0.85. Above this mass fraction value, the material follows a mixtures rule. To support our observations, we prepared composite laminates with the CNTF and achieved a modulus as high 65GPa·SG⁻¹ and tensile strength 0.75GPa·SG⁻¹.

At the same time, when the CNT fibre is stretched, a shift of 2D Raman band due to the stretching C-C bond is observed. In the case of the CNTF embedded in a polymer matrix, the rate of the shift of 2D Raman band varies linearly with the matrix's Young's modulus ($\sim 30\text{cm}^{-1}\cdot\%^{-1}$ in the case of polystyrene). We suggest that the increase in fibre modulus upon infiltration is due to polymer chains binding adjacent bundle and thus transferring stress to larger the fraction of elements. The fibre Young's modulus increase depends approximately linearly the modulus of the polymer matrix. Thus, the modulus of any CNT fibre composite can be predicted only measuring the intrinsic properties of CNT fibre and from knowledge of the modulus of the matrix.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is an ever increasing plethora of nanomaterials becoming available in sufficient quantities to integrate them into macroscopic structures, typically in composites where they coexist with a matrix. Examples include the widely studied nanocarbons (CNTs, graphene) [1,2] metal nanowires [3], inorganic nanowires [4], organic whiskers [5], etc. This has been widely seen as a promising route to translate their exciting properties onto a macroscopic length scale, particularly mechanical and electrical. In this quest, it has become apparent that dispersing nanoparticles as fillers becomes rapidly ineffective at volume fractions above 1% due to aggregation and processing difficulties intrinsic to nanoparticle dispersion. Instead, the controlled assembly of nanobuilding blocks into macroscopic structures with preferential alignment parallel to the nanocarbon axis of interest (nanotube/wire axis or in-plane for 2D material) has proven more effective. Continuous fibres and films made up of CNTs, graphene, and their combinations are now routinely produced by wet spinning [6,7], drawing from arrays, and direct spinning from CVD [8,9], some of them in semi-industrial quantities.

CNT fibres, which have been studied for over 10 years longer than graphene fibres, already rival or outperform reference high-performance materials in terms of specific mechanical properties (similar to carbon fibre), electrical conductivity (2.5 of copper per unit mass [10]) and composite performance

[11–13].

A unique aspect shared by these fibres and films is the combination of high-performance properties and an exceptionally high surface area and porosity. At around $200\text{m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, their BET specific surface is about 1000 greater than that of a traditional material such as a CF filament, with the implication that their interfaces with gases, liquids and solids is also exceptionally large and thus plays a critical part in their physical properties. This porosity is reminiscent of the bottom-up assembly process and results in a hierarchical structure made up individual nanobuilding blocks that associate in nanocrystals (e.g. bundles), which then form microfibrils and subsequently a filament. Such a hierarchical structure is perhaps similar to a natural fibre [14] or a cotton yarn but otherwise unprecedented as a synthetic material.

As a result of this yarn-like porous structure these materials have outstanding flexibility in bending [15] and can therefore be knitted and knotted, they can host multifunctional nanoparticles, and can readily be infiltrated with liquids [16] and polymers [17]. The ingress of liquid molecules into the fibres has been shown to lead to sensing properties, non-Ohmic field-modulated behaviour [17], and used to produce new hybrid materials, whereas the penetration of polymer molecules has resulted in a superb integration in polymer matrix composites, as reported by Wang *et al.* [12]. In spite of these examples of successful materials, it is surprising how little is understood about the mechanical properties of these fibers when infiltrated with different polymers and liquids.

In this work we show that the introduction of polymer into the fibres enhances stress transfer between the load-bearing elements. By comparing the Raman shift of the 2D peak during in-situ tensile testing of specimens, we establish the role of the polymer as a stress transfer element. Results for CNTF-composites with different polymer matrices, hence having different bulk Young's modulus, suggest that stress transfer is not univocally determined by the fibre properties, but depends on the intrinsic characteristics of the matrix in which CNTFs are embedded. We propose a simple model to determine fibre properties for arbitrary matrices by applying a correction factor to the properties of the dry (i.e. non-infiltrated) fibre, which enables then subsequent use of standard composite theory to predict properties of composite structures with multiple filaments such as an unidirectional laminate.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The hierarchical structure of CNT fibres and the consequent strong interaction with foreign molecules can be observed in Figure 1. The Figure 1a shows a comparative sequence when a drop of epoxy resin is released on the surface of graphite and CNTF films. We used graphite in order to demonstrate that the interaction between the matrix (epoxy resin) and the reinforcement (carbon fibre) in a traditional composite is limited to the surface, unlike what happens in our CNTF that the resin is hosted inside the film.

Figure 1: a) Image sequence of views from above of epoxy infiltration process of graphite (left) and CNTF films (right). b) SEM pictures of CNTF film as spun.

The SEM micrograph of a non-infiltrated fiber (Figure 1b) shows the preferential alignment of CNTs parallel to each other and to the fiber axis which nevertheless are imperfectly packed and therefore give rise to a substantial porosity and surface area accessible to small molecules. It's explain because when such structure is exposed to epoxy resin, it rapidly wicks due to the strong capillary forces and fills the internal pores of the fiber.

The first question then is how the polymer contributes to the mechanical properties of the infiltrated fiber. We study this by plotting stress-strain curves of CNTFs before and after polymer infiltration, and by normalizing the stress normalized to the composite's specific gravity (Figure 2). The use of specific properties avoids defining cross sections and provides a direct measure of the enhancement in mechanical properties that arise due to the presence of polymer. If the polymer simply contributes to the composite mechanical properties in non-interacting manner, for example as a coating, then the properties of the resulting material would approximately follow a simple rule of mixtures (inset Figure 2), in which the polymer would reduce specific properties of the mixture. However, Figure 2 clearly demonstrates that the polymer enhance as much the Young's modulus in the linear region as to the stress at break.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curves at 30 mm gauge length of non-infiltrated CNT fiber film (dashed line) and epoxy-infiltrated CNT fiber film with fiber mass fraction (w_f) of 0.951 (solid line). The inset corresponds to the typical behavior of a rule of mixtures, commonly used in composites theories to predict the Young's modulus in axial direction of the fiber.

Such enhancement can be directly measured by in-situ Raman spectroscopy during tensile testing [18–20]. Under tensile (compressive) strain, Raman active modes are shifted from their original position, since the vibrational frequency of molecular bonds changes. Thus, by following the evolution of the 2D band, which unequivocally corresponds to CNTs in the fibre, we could obtain the stress being transferred to them, when acting as load-bearing elements in the composite. In order to determine the modulus of our CNTF composites from the Raman spectra, the ratio between the 2D peak downshift and tensile strain can be extracted and compared to the values for an individual graphene layer in a highly crystalline carbon fibre. This enables us to convert the peak downshift magnitude into stress for determining the modulus, as shown by *Young et al.* [21], and to estimate how efficiently the nanotubes in the fibre are being collectively strained [22]. Figure 3a presents a plot of the 2D Raman mode position against the fibre strain for both, the dry fibre and polymer infiltrated fibres (with TPU and PS, as soft and hard matrices, respectively). Graphs are nearly mirror images of those in Figure 3, again, indicating that the addition of polymer increases stress transfer to the CNTs per unit fibre strain. The calculated slopes magnitude in the initial part of the curve come out as 8.65 ± 1.17 , 10.86 ± 1.25 and $29.35 \pm 3.35 \text{ cm}^{-1} \cdot \%^{-1}$ for the dry, TPU-infiltrated and PS-infiltrated, respectively, confirming the increase in fibre modulus, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: (a) 2D Raman peak position under tensile strain of dry individual filaments of CNT fibre (squares), and embedded in TPU (circles) and PS (triangles). (b) Plot of slope magnitude of 2D Raman peak position $\left(\frac{\Delta \text{Pos}(2D)}{\Delta \epsilon} \right)$ versus Young's modulus of infiltrated polymer.

The Raman-calculated modulus varies from 62.5 to 79.4 $\text{GPa} \cdot \text{SG}^{-1}$ for a dry fibre. Its bulk modulus of 14.5 $\text{GPa} \cdot \text{SG}^{-1}$, is in fact a manifestation of a non-uniform stress distribution throughout along it, conceptually similar to that in a network of elastic elements of different stiffness in series. The stiffer elements correspond to highly aligned closed-packed bundles, whereas the less stiff ones correspond to misaligned CNTs with limited contact between. These latter elements provide larger longitudinal strain for a given load. The addition of polymer increases the overall stress transfer to the fibre [18,23] but the non-uniform stress transfer prevails because of the remaining orientational heterogeneity. These considerations are consistent with results observed by *Beese et al.* [24] and others authors, in which covalent junctions between individual CNT bundles could promote reinforcement

Raman enables analysing only the surface portion of materials, since the excitation source has UV-NIR energy and coincides with the frequency range in which graphitic materials tend to absorb the most. Nevertheless, we believe that Raman-extracted stress fields should reflect the bulk behaviour of our composites because: **a)** The fibres have a uniform degree of CNT orientation down to the nanoscale, with no indication of a core-sheath structure [18,25], and **b)** we have observed average downshift factors that are well in agreement with those for the bulk fibre.

In CNT fibres stress is transferred by shear between neighbouring elements and thus depends on the overlap of load-bearing elements [26,27]. The low shear strength of graphite (30kPa) and the imperfect packing of bundles limit the number of elements that bear the load. The addition of polymer enables neighbouring bundles, which are otherwise not in contact, to transfer load. This increases the number of load-bearing elements along the fibre axis and thus enhances its effective properties. Therefore, although Raman measurements correspond to neighbouring bundles that are on the surface and have reduced contacts, this situation mimics exactly what is found at the inner fibre portions, where adjacent bundles are separated by thin void areas or pores. Hence, the enhancement of stress transfer that has been extracted from Raman, can be indeed taken as a measure of how the bulk material is affected by the infiltration of polymer and how this activates bundles that were unstressed prior to infiltration.

The average slope magnitudes in the linear region of the curves (<1% strain) of Figure 3a, come out as 8.65 ± 1.17 , 10.86 ± 1.25 and $29.35 \pm 3.35 \text{cm}^{-1} \cdot \%^{-1}$ for the dry, TPU fibers and PS, respectively, which follows the moduli of the infiltrating medium $0 < 74.5 \pm 50.2 < 1248 \pm 39.59 \text{ MPa}$. This trend was confirmed using additional matrices, as shown Figure 3b, where the negative magnitude of the slope increases approximately in a linear fashion with matrix Young's modulus, that is, the stiffer the matrix the larger the increase in fiber properties.

In the infiltrated fiber the matrix plays a similar role by "joining" neighboring elements that were separated by open pores and had therefore limited stress transfer before the introduction of polymer. A conceptually similar system is a CF fabric, which has limited cooperative stress transfer (poor properties) until it is infused with a matrix that then binds the load bearing filaments together and enables the transfer of stress to them. Fitting experimental data on "Raman modulus" $\left(\frac{\Delta P_{os}(2D)}{\Delta \varepsilon} \right)$ against matrix modulus (E_m) we obtain an expression of the form:

$$\frac{\Delta P_{os}(2D)_C}{\Delta \varepsilon} = \frac{\Delta P_{os}(2D)_D}{\Delta \varepsilon} + a \cdot E_m \quad (1.1)$$

Where subscripts 'C' and 'D' are referred to the composite and the non-infiltrated CNT fibre, respectively. And the value of 'a' was calculated as $-0.01651 \text{cm}^{-1} \cdot \%^{-1} \cdot \text{MPa}^{-1}$. This first approximation, while obviating degree of polymer infiltration and adhesion is nevertheless useful in the prediction of composite properties.

An important implication of Figure 3 is that unlike traditional fibres (e.g. CF) which have defined properties that can be used to predict composite properties, CNT fibres have properties that depend on the choice of matrix and to the extent at which the fibre the porous structure of the fibre is infiltrated.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The results and discussion above rationalize the effects of polymer infiltration into porous CNT fibres and provide a first method to predict the mechanical properties of larger composite structures that could be obtained upon their incorporation. These results reveal details about the deformation mechanism of the fibre, which are in principle applicable to other macroscopic assemblies of imperfectly packed and weakly interacting nanobuilding blocks.

This simple model requires to know the in-situ Raman data during tensile testing $\left(\frac{\Delta P_{os}(2D)}{\Delta \varepsilon} \right)$ currently ignores the fibre/matrix chemistry and the degree of infiltration of large molecular weight polymers. Work is in progress to take these factors into account. In spite of these limitations, through the correction of the dry fibre modulus it is possible to obtain a first prediction of the properties of the fibre in a polymer matrix and thus engineer more complex structures with arrays of fibres and thus

begin to exploit the properties of these nanostructured materials in advanced structural applications.

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